
THE ROLE OF GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES IN SHAPING COGNITION AND CULTURE: A COGNITIVE LINGUISTIC PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation. This approach explains the connection between language structure and cognitive processes, suggesting that categories such as "time," "activity," and "place" reflect how individuals perceive and organize reality. Grammatical categories, including tense and aspect, convey not only time-related information but also nuances about the nature of actions, their duration, and completion. The present study explores the impact of grammatical categories on thought processes and highlights the role of language in reflecting culture, worldview, and social dynamics. Additionally, cognitive linguistics offers insight into how different languages categorize time and events, exemplified by variations in tense structures across languages like Russian.

Keywords: *Cognitive linguistics, grammatical categories, tense, aspect, language and cognition, worldview, language structure, time categories, semantics, syntax, cultural differences.*

Annotatsiya . Bu yondashuv til tuzilishi va kognitiv jarayonlar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni tushuntirib, "vaqt", "faoliyat" va "joy" kabi kategoriyalar shaxslarning voqelikni qanday idrok etishi va tashkil etishini aks ettirishini ko'rsatadi. Grammatik kategoriyalar, jumladan, zamon va aspekt nafaqat vaqt bilan bog'liq ma'lumotlarni, balki harakatlarning tabiati, ularning davomiyligi va tugallanishi haqidagi nuanslarni ham beradi. Ushbu tadqiqot grammatik kategoriyalarning fikrlash jarayonlariga ta'sirini o'rganadi va tilning madaniyat, dunyoqarash va ijtimoiy dinamikani aks

ettirishdagi rolini ta'kidlaydi. Bundan tashqari, kognitiv lingvistika turli tillar vaqt va hodisalarni qanday tasniflashi haqida tushuncha beradi, bunga misol sifatida rus tili kabi tillardagi zamon tuzilmalarining o'zgarishi misol bo'ladi.

Tayanch soʻzlar: *Kognitiv tilshunoslik, grammatik kategoriyalar, zamon, aspekt, til va bilish, dunyoqarash, til tuzilishi, zamon kategoriyalari, semantika, sintaksis, madaniy farqlar.*

Аннотация. Этот подход объясняет связь между языковой структурой и когнитивными процессами, предполагая, что такие категории, как «время», «деятельность» и «место», отражают то, как люди воспринимают и организуют реальность. Грамматические категории, в том числе время и вид, передают не только временную информацию, но и нюансы характера действий, их продолжительности и завершения. Настоящее исследование исследует влияние грамматических категорий на мыслительные процессы и подчеркивает роль языка в отражении культуры, мировоззрения и социальной динамики. Кроме того, когнитивная лингвистика дает представление о том, как разные языки классифицируют время и события, примером чему служат различия во временных структурах в таких языках, как русский.

Ключевые слова: *Когнитивная лингвистика, грамматические категории, время, вид, язык и познание, мировоззрение, языковая структура, временные категории, семантика, синтаксис, культурные различия.*

Introduction. Cognitive linguistics is a branch of linguistics that studies language in relation to human consciousness and understanding. At the heart of cognitive linguistics is how language expresses and describes human thinking and worldview. This approach is based on understanding language as a complex system in relation to the human being and his life, rather than considering it only as a system of rules and structures. Grammatical categories make up the main structures of the language, give meaning and function, and play an important role in communication. Grammatical categories are categories that form language components such as meaning, time, person, situation, and they are one of the main elements of language.

From the point of view of cognitive linguistics, grammatical categories include not only structural but also semantic aspects of language. This further increases the importance of grammatical categories in understanding and using language.

Main body. In cognitive linguistics, grammatical categories are viewed not only as syntactic or morphological features, but as tools developed for how language is used to make sense of the external world. For example, categories such as "time", "activity", "place" are based not only on the rules of grammar, but also on the manifestations of the human mind. Grammatical categories reflect how people perceive the world and how they organize it (Lakoff, 1987).

Cognitive linguistics links grammatical categories with the cognitive processes of language creation and emphasizes their semantic importance. Grammatical categories are closely related to the structure of the language, through which the meaning structure of the language is formed. For example, the meaning of actions such as "to collect" or "to be" is actually understood through their specific rules of grammar. In cognitive linguistics, grammatical categories include not only syntactic symbols, but also semantic elements related to them. Examples of this are tense and aspect categories. These categories are not only used to indicate time, but also to indicate how an action or event took place, its duration, or its completion. Such grammatical structures are often seen as a means by which language reflects the thoughts and feelings formed by individual linguists (Langacker, 1991). Another interesting aspect of cognitive linguistics is that grammatical categories reflect not only individual thinking, but also culture, worldview, and social change. Cognitive linguistics raises the question of how the worldview and thinking of language users is shaped by grammar (Evans & Green, 2006).

The appearance of grammatical categories in cognitive linguistics requires consideration of social and cultural foundations. For example, some languages have grammatical categories of gender, and these categories reflect cultural and social roles (Whorf, 1956). In addition, in cognitive linguistics, linguists emphasize that the subjective experience of the linguist, his worldview and cultural values are also

important in the study of grammatical categories. From this point of view, grammatical categories reflect not only the form of language, but also the worldview that is formed through language.

Conclusion. In cognitive linguistics, grammatical categories, as one of the main building blocks of language, reflect a person's worldview, his thinking, and his interactions in social conditions. Grammatical categories are an important tool in creating not only the structure of language, but also meaning and understanding. Cognitive linguistics studies grammatical categories in linguistics not only at the syntactic or morphological level, but also from the perspective of human thinking and cognitive processes. In cognitive linguistics, grammatical categories are an important tool for understanding how the human mind works through language, how it organizes the world and establishes mutual relations.

RESOURCES

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